

Roadmap for SSHRC Aid to Scholarly Journals: Adopting Best Practices in Diamond Open Access

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This document is also [available in French](#).

Adapted from:

[Feuille de route pour répondre aux exigences du FRQ en matière de libre accès diamant](#)

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Introduction

In the summer of 2025, the Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council (SSHRC) announced its new [Aid to Scholarly Journals](#) (ASJ) program. The competition introduces new requirements for eligible journals for the next competition, scheduled for 2028. By 2028, SSHRC will require that all journals be made available in immediate open access without article processing charges (also known as diamond open access), have an open licence and be aligned with the criteria of the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) to be eligible for funding. There is no requirement to fulfil these criteria in advance of applying for the 2025 competition; however, journals must include an *outline of future direction* providing a transition plan to immediate open access (OA) without a subscription or APCs and/or a plan to align with DOAJ inclusion criteria, including adopting an open licence, with their application to the 2025 competition.

Coalition Publica, as a partnership between Érudit and PKP working closely with university libraries, is committed to supporting journals in the transition to [diamond open access](#) and in adhering to best practices in digital publishing. We have worked with over forty journals to make the transition to OA and with countless others to understand DOAJ requirements and open licences. We are pleased to provide this road map as one of the tools available to you as you undertake a transition to an open access business model and/or align the journal with best practices in OA publishing.

Who should use the road map, and how?

The road map is meant primarily for scholarly journals, with or without an embargo period/moving wall, that do not already use an open licence and that intend to comply with the criteria laid out in the 2025 SSHRC ASJ program. While it makes reference to Érudit and Open Journal Systems (OJS) throughout the document, any journal may follow the guiding principles whether or not they use either of these platforms.

A note for journals funded by the Fonds de recherche du Québec (FRQ): the FRQ program has slightly different criteria than those of the SSHRC ASJ program. We recommend following the guide [Feuille de route pour répondre aux exigences du FRQ en matière de libre accès diamant](#) (in French only), which will ensure your journal is eligible for both programs.

A flexible checklist rather than a guide

The road map is not a guide and does not explain *how* to execute the steps necessary to transition to diamond OA; rather it is a checklist to use during your planning so that you do

not forget an essential element of the process. Ideally, you will use this tool in combination with other resources, some of which are mentioned in this document.

The road map is designed to fit the largest range of situations possible. Every journal exists in its own unique set of circumstances; certain steps or aspects might not apply to your specific situation. Therefore, you do not have to read the entire document from start to finish. Use the table of contents to find the sections related to major milestones and consult the ones that apply to your situation.

To help you plan, we have proposed a [timeline](#) to 2028 roughly divided in three main phases.

1. Summer 2025 to Summer 2026: gather information and begin preliminary planning for compliance with requirements of the ASJ grant.
2. Summer 2026 to Spring 2027: make decisions on how to comply with the requirements of the ASJ grant.
3. Summer 2027 to Summer 2028: implement changes to your publishing practices to comply with the requirements of the ASJ grant.

Unless stated otherwise, this document assumes a scenario where the journal transitions to OA for 2028, as required by SSHRC ASJ. Of course, based on your situation and your capacity, you might want to plan shorter timelines.

Who can help you with this process?

Every journal's situation is different. Depending on your hosting arrangement and distribution channels, you may be able to avail yourself of help from the following:

- If the journal is disseminated through *Érudit* or participates in *Coalition Publica*, you can reach out to your contact at *Érudit*.
- If the journal is hosted or published by a university library, you may be able to ask your publishing librarian for support. Although the nature and degree of support will vary from library to library, your publishing librarian *may* be able to help you with certain steps, particularly around open licences and adhering to the DOAJ criteria, in collaboration with *Érudit* if applicable.
- If the journal is published by an organization or by a unit within a university (including the library), you may have access to legal and procurement advice.
- If the journal is involved in any publishing/disciplinary specific associations, you could reach out to other journals who are/have been in similar positions for experiential advice.

We have provided more detailed information about the services you may expect to receive from the above in [Appendix 2](#). We've also included links to relevant resources that apply generally to the process rather than specific steps.

Before starting

Before diving in, we recommend that you carefully read over the [Aid to Scholarly Journals: September 2025 Competition](#) details on the SSHRC website, as well as the [Instructions for applying](#).

The three main changes to the SSHRC ASJ program that are the focus of this roadmap are:

- Open access dissemination in time for the 2028 ASJ competition
 - If the journal is on Érudit: a journal's transition to OA on Érudit can only take place on January 1st of each year, after notification by the journal no later than September 1st of the previous year. So, if you plan to transition to OA in 2028, you must inform your main contact at Érudit of this decision **before September 1st, 2027**.
- Use of an open licence (e.g. Creative Commons licence) for the dissemination of new articles in time for the 2028 ASJ competition
- Be listed in the DOAJ or meet all the criteria for inclusion in time for the 2028 ASJ competition
 - One of the DOAJ criteria states that "Before applying to DOAJ, a new or flipped journal must demonstrate a publishing history of more than one year or have published at least ten open access research articles". This specific requirement from the DOAJ will not be taken into account for eligibility in the 2028 ASJ program.

It may be a good idea to organize a kick-off meeting with the people who will be actively contributing to the transition, as well as with those who will be able to support you such as the staff at Érudit and your librarians, if applicable.

Gathering information

Recommended timeframe: Summer 2025 to Summer 2026

Carry out an environmental scan and inventory

Objective: Understand the journal's current practices and the contexts and values of the journal's larger environment, in order to prepare for the next phases of the road map.

Elements to identify

- Is the journal required to comply with requirements from its host institutions, its partners or granting agencies other than SSHRC?
 - For journals funded by the FRQ: see the [Feuille de route pour répondre aux exigences du FRQ en matière de libre accès diamant](#)
- Are there common funder requirements its authors are required to comply with? For instance:
 - Many funders require an open licence on published articles
 - Authors may need to retain their copyright
 - Authors may be required to self-archive their articles
- What are the typical practices within the field? What are the practices of other, similar journals? Are there reservations concerning open access in your community?
- Take stock of your workflow and publishing practices.
 - If you don't already use one, are there editorial management and dissemination platforms like Open Journal Systems (OJS) that could help you manage the journal operations?
- Which websites (OJS site, Érudit, association website, etc.) contain information about the journal that may need to be updated?

Tools to help you out

- Search the [DOAJ journal list](#) and [Érudit journal list](#) to find other OA journals in the same field
- [Tri-Agency Open Access Policy on Publications](#) (under revision; will likely require self-archiving for grantees)
- [Open Policy Finder](#)

Identify stakeholders

Objective: Identify the individuals and entities with decision-making or financial authority for the journal, and all other participants in the journal's activities.

Elements to identify

- Legal or decision-making entity/Affiliate institution, such as:
 - University or department
 - Scholarly society or association

- Publishing house or university press
- Other
- Journal team and committees
- Permanent and contractual staff
- Library providing a support service
- Dissemination partners (Érudit and other dissemination platforms that manage subscriptions for the journal)
- Individual and institutional subscribers, recipients of courtesy copies
- Beneficiaries of journal revenues (other than the journal itself)

Take stock of contracts and agreements

Objective: Identify all agreements that legally bind the journal to external individuals or entities to determine the impact of these agreements on a transition to open access, and vice versa.

Contracts and agreements to identify

- With a publishing house or press
- With dissemination or subscription management platforms (i.e., Érudit, JSTOR)
- With indexers and content providers (ex. EBSCO, ProQuest)
- With service providers (i.e., publishing services, printers)
- With journal authors

Identify the journal's formats

Objective: Identify all the formats in which the journal is disseminated to analyze the costs and revenues of each, as needed.

Elements to consider

- Print format (on demand, frequency, number of copies, etc.)
- Digital formats (PDF, HTML, ePub, etc.)

Aligning copyright and licensing with open access standards

Recommended timeframe: Summer 2025 to Summer 2026

Summer 2025

Summer 2026

Spring 2027

Summer 2028

Understand open licences

Objective: Understand the nature and impacts of using an open licence, required by SSHRC for 2028, to appropriately plan its implementation.

Actions

- Learn more about [Creative Commons licences](#)
- Plan an information session with the editorial team to discuss the resources that can support you in this process (some are listed below)
- Determine which open licence would be most appropriate for the journal
- Identify elements to modify to account for this new licence (contracts with authors, information on the website(s), policies, etc.)

Tools to help you out

- A short [introduction to Creative Commons licences](#)
- University of Alberta Libraries' [Brief Guide to Creative Commons Licensing Options](#)
- Public Knowledge Project's guides on [Open Access policies](#) and [Copyright and licensing](#)

Rethink the journal's copyright policy

Objective: Reflect on who holds the copyright for published articles and determine if this policy should be modified in the context of an open licence. Open licences often, but not necessarily, see the author retaining copyright rather than transferring it to the journal. Granting agencies sometimes require authors to retain copyright, as indicated in the [draft of the revised Tri-Agency Open Access Policy on Publications](#).

Actions

- Plan an information session with the editorial team and other identified resources that can support you in this process
- If a change in copyright ownership is considered:
 - Gather the necessary information for the journal leadership to make a decision
 - Identify the elements that need to be modified and take these into account (contracts with authors, information on the website, copyright policy, etc.)

Verify compliance with DOAJ criteria

Objective: Plan future issues by taking into account the criteria established by the DOAJ that influence the contents of journal issues (i.e., [endogeny](#), [special issues](#)). To be eligible for the 2028 SSHRC ASJ program, journals are required to meet the directory's inclusion criteria, although submitting an application is optional.

Actions

- Review the DOAJ criteria for inclusion and take note of any information that may be missing from the journal's websites
 - For journals on Érudit: request a preliminary analysis from your point of contact
- Take into account the elements that need to be amended in future issues, if needed

Tools to help you out

- The DOAJ's [application form](#), [guide to applying](#), and [transparency & best practices](#) outline the requirements for indexing in the DOAJ and provide advice on compliance.

Consider a self-archiving (repository) policy (optional)

Objective: Develop a formal self-archiving (repository) policy in order to comply with best practices in OA and with funding requirements for authors concerned with Plan S and other policies (including the [draft of the revised Tri-Agency Open Access Policy on Publications](#)).

Actions

- Consider your policy with regards to authors sharing the submitted version, accepted version and published version in a repository
- Consider how to make the accepted versions of the article available to authors
- Adopt a self-archiving policy and update the publishing contract accordingly
- Communicate the self-archiving policy on every website related to the journal

Tools to help you out

- University of Alberta Libraries' [Journal policy toolkit](#)
- Public Knowledge Project's guide on [Journal Policies and Workflows](#)
- [Draft, Revised Tri-Agency Open Access Policy on Publications \(2025\)](#)

Budgetary analysis

Recommended timeframe: Summer 2025 to Summer 2026

Analyze revenues

Objective: Understand the journal's current and future revenues to evaluate potential business models for a transition to open access.

Actions

1. Analyze **current revenue sources** and identify those that may no longer be available to you in an OA business model
 - A. Grants and direct institutional contributions
 - B. Subscription revenues from printed copies
 - C. Subscription revenues from digital (all dissemination platforms)
 - D. Unit sales of printed or digital copies
 - E. Revenues from Access Copyright, Copibec or other rights management organizations
 - F. Other revenues (gifts, memberships, conference organizations, etc.)
2. Identify **potential new sources of revenue** and explore options
 - A. For journals on Érudit: Partnership for Open Access (POA) (automatic for Érudit journals without APCs after removing embargo/moving wall)
 - B. Other options to explore:
 - i. Grants and direct contributions from affiliated institutions or organizations
 - ii. Collective funds that support open access
 - iii. Gifts and donations (previous subscribed institutions, academic or other foundations, socio-financing campaigns, etc.)
 - iv. Fundraising and gifts unrelated to article publication.
 - v. Sales of printed copies (subscription, on demand, anthologies, etc.)

- vi. Value-add services (organizing conferences, popular science content, courses and training, etc.)
- vii. Partnerships with professional associations

Tools to help you out

- [Budgetary analysis worksheet](#)

Analyze expenses

Objective: Understand the journal's expenses and cash flow to evaluate potential business models for a transition to open access. If necessary, identify areas for savings in case the loss of subscription revenues results in a budget shortfall.

Actions

1. Identify current expenses
 - A. Salaries
 - B. Printed version (printing, mailing costs, storage, etc.)
 - C. Graphical design and formatting
 - D. Proofreading and Translation
 - E. Hosting (website, OJS, etc.)
 - F. For journals on Érudit: digital production fees
 - G. Other fees
2. Identify areas for savings
 - A. Salaries
 - i. Consider the possibility of using shared services¹
 - ii. Automate or simplify certain time-consuming processes
 - B. Printed version
 - i. Discontinue the printed version or reduce the number of copies
 - ii. Consider on-demand printing
 - C. Graphic design and typesetting
 - i. Simplify the article template
 - ii. Hire graphic design students/offer an internship
 - iii. For journals with Érudit: subscribe to Érudit's automatic PDF generation service (only available with full XML processing)
 - D. Proofreading and translation
 - i. Consider the possibility of sharing some services

¹ Shared services here refer to the community-based human and digital resources that may be available to you, including university-based support for digital infrastructure, co-ops or part time work for graduate students in library sciences or publishing programs, freelance or community-based professional networks such as [CALJ](#), [Editors Canada](#), etc. This could also mean pooling resources between journals from the same institution/network to hire someone.

- E. Hosting (website, OJS, etc.)
 - i. Consider the possibility of using shared services
- F. Other fees

Tools to help you out

- [Budgetary analysis worksheet](#)

Settling on a plan of action

Recommended timeframe: Summer 2026 - Spring 2027

Make decisions

Objective: Present the analysis and potential changes to the journal's business model to stakeholders who have the authority required to approve operational changes.

Decision factors

- Present and the results of your budgetary analysis and approve the open access business model
- Set the timeline, notably these milestones:
 - The first issue or volume which sees the changes implemented
 - The official date of the transition to complete open access
 - For journals on Érudit: this date must be set to January 1st of any year to respect the agreement with Érudit
 - Consider other agreements you have, whether the transition will be aligned with a fiscal year or the calendar year
- Approve the [choice of an open licence](#)
- Approve the [copyright policy](#), if needed
- Approve the [self-archiving \(repository\) policy](#), if applicable

Inform partners

Objective: Communicate with partners with whom you have contractual agreements who could be affected by the above decisions.

Actions

- Identify among the [inventoried contracts](#) those that need to be modified, who you need to contact and the timelines to respect
- For journals on Érudit: inform your contact as soon as possible.
- Inform other partners as applicable

Implementing the plan

Recommended timeframe: Summer 2027 - Summer 2028

Implement the OA business model

Objective: Adapt the journal's practices to the new business model.

Actions

- Establish agreements with new service providers, if applicable (i.e., shared services)
- Identify where financial procedures will be affected and adapt them to the new business model
- Implement processes to obtain new sources of revenue

Modify contracts

Objective: Add, modify or renegotiate clauses to adapt [contracts](#) to the journal's new business model.

Actions and specific timelines

- For journals on Érudit: modify contracts with Érudit, if applicable:

- Sign the agreement rescinding the commercialization contract with Érudit by **September 1, 2027 at the latest** (or September 1st of the year prior to the transition to open access)
- Sign the amendment to your dissemination contract to add the open access publishing clause by **September 1, 2027 at the latest** (or September 1st of the year prior to the transition to open access)
- Modify contracts with other dissemination platforms, indexers and aggregators:
 - Identify clauses that can be added or modified
 - Contact the parties whose contracts need to be modified (indexers, dissemination platforms), inform them of the transition to open access and request modifications to certain clauses
 - Specific timeline:** *based on contract renewal dates or the process established by the partner*
- Modify or implement a contract with authors to account for the journal's new reality:
 - Add a clause on dissemination with an open licence
 - Modify the attribution of copyright, if needed
 - Specific timeline:** *before opening submissions for the first issue published in open access*
 - Inform authors of the changes to the publication contract
- Modify the contract with the printer (if applicable:):
 - Terminate or modify the contract (number of copies, etc.)
 - Specific timeline:** *based on the dates in the contract or the date of publication of the first issue published in open access*
- Modify the contracts with other service providers or contractual partners:
 - Terminate or modify the contract:
 - Specific timeline:** *based on the dates in the contract or the date of publication of the first issue published in open access*

Update editorial management tools and website

Specific timeline for this step: *Before the call for submissions for the first issue published in OA*

Objective: Ensure that the changes made to the journal are reflected in the tools, configuration, and information on the website.

Actions

- Change the configuration and settings of the editorial management tool (i.e., OJS) based on the decisions made concerning copyright attribution and licence use

- Modify relevant email templates sent to authors
- Update the website(s) with the new policies for copyright, licencing, and self archiving (if applicable), including instructions for authors
 - Note the first volume and issue for which the new policies apply
- Plan the removal of the embargo/moving wall for articles on the date of the transition to OA, if necessary

Modify article templates

Specific timeline: *Before accepting the first article that will be published in the first OA issue.*

Objective: If the journal is responsible for the graphic design of its articles, integrate the relevant changes into the article template.

Actions

- Communicate with the person responsible for the graphic design
- Articulate your open licence statement and the copyright holder, and incorporate these into your article template
- If this was identified as a cost-saving measure, simplify the article template

Inform stakeholders

Objective: Communicate with stakeholders to inform them of the transition at the appropriate time through the appropriate channel.

Actions

- Communicate with authors about the transition and the change to the contracts
- Communicate with subscribers and the recipients of courtesy copies
- Communicate with your readership and community (social media, newsletter, editorial note, etc.)

Resources to help you out

- Your contacts at dissemination platforms can provide you with a list of your subscribers

Ensure alignment with remaining DOAJ criteria

Objective: Align with the [inclusion criteria](#) of the DOAJ. Although submitting an application is not required within the SSHRC ASJ 2025 granting period, inclusion in the DOAJ can increase the reputation, visibility and discoverability of the journal.

Actions

- Verify all remaining criteria that have not been met by your choice of open licence and copyright.
 - Execute the necessary steps to meet these requirements
- For journals on Érudit: speak to your point of contact about the DOAJ support service.
 - Request a complete analysis of the journal by Érudit
- If the journal is hosted or published by a university library, you may be able to ask your publishing librarian for support.
- Submit an application to the DOAJ (optional)

Beyond the transition

Your journal is now a part of the ever-growing diamond OA community, congratulations! Take the time to appreciate and celebrate the effort required for this transition. We always appreciate hearing from journals about their experiences with open access so please keep in touch! You can always contact us at info@coalition-publi.ca

Here are some points to keep in mind for the future:

- *Make the journal more visible and discoverable*
Several indexes and databases can provide the journal with even more visibility. If your journal is hosted or published by a library, your librarians may be able to help you identify the most relevant ones for you and support you during the process.
- *Keep the information up to date*
You have probably spent a lot of time updating your websites to align the journal with the DOAJ criteria. It is important that you now keep applying best practices and update the information on your websites, including your DOAJ file, Érudit About page, and OJS site, as applicable.
- *Stay informed*
Scholarly publishing is in constant evolution. The journal can only benefit if you stay

up to date on technical innovations, funding opportunities and best practices. [Visit our website](#) or sign up for the [Érudit](#) and [PKP](#) newsletters to stay in the loop.

- *Prepare a post-transition assessment*

After a few years of transition, it may be worthwhile to assess your new situation: Did you receive more or fewer submissions? Is your pool of authors more diverse? How have your readership statistics changed? Did you have to adapt some work processes or change your approach? Share your experience with your colleagues from other journals.

Appendix 1: Recommended timeline

Milestones in this timeline flagged with **(É)** mean there is a specific deadline required for journals disseminated on Eruudit, refer to the appropriate section of the guide for more detail. Any journal may wish to follow this timeline in order to comply with the conditions of the ASJ grant in a timely fashion. The bullet points in this timeline correspond to the activities outlined in this roadmap.

Timeframe	Activity
Until Summer 2026	<p>In this phase you should gather information and begin preliminary planning for compliance with requirements of the ASJ grant.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Gathering information <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Carry out an environmental scan and inventory ○ Identify stakeholders ○ Take stock of contracts and agreements ○ Identify the journal's formats ● Aligning copyright and licensing with OA standards <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Understand open licences ○ Rethink the journal's copyright policy ○ Verify compliance with DOAJ criteria ○ Consider a self-archiving (repository) policy (optional) ● Budgetary analysis <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Analyze revenues ○ Analyze expenses
Summer 2026 - Spring 2027	<p>In this phase you will develop an action plan for complying with the requirements of the ASJ grant.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Settling on a plan of action <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Make decisions (É) ○ Inform partners (É)
Summer 2027 - Summer 2028	<p>In this phase you will implement the action plan for complying with the requirements of the ASJ grant.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Implementing the plan <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Implement the OA business model ○ Modify contracts (É) ○ Update editorial management tools and the website ○ Modify article templates ○ Inform stakeholders ○ Ensure alignment with remaining DOAJ criteria

Appendix 2: Who can help you with this process?

Every journal's situation is different. Depending on your hosting arrangement and distribution channels, you may be able to avail yourself of help from the following:

- If you are disseminated by Érudit or participate in Coalition Publica, you can reach out to your contact at Érudit for help with:
 - Taking stock of contracts and agreements
 - Identifying the journal's formats
 - Verifying compliance with DOAJ criteria
 - Analyzing expenses and revenues as related to Érudit, Coalition Publica, and the Partnership for Open Access
 - Modifying your contract with Érudit
 - Submitting an application to DOAJ

- If the journal is hosted or published by a university library, you may be able to ask your publishing librarian for support. Although the nature and degree of support will vary from library to library, your publishing librarian *may* be able to help you with:
 - Understanding open licences
 - Rethinking copyright policy
 - Developing a self-archiving (repository) policy
 - Modifying author agreements
 - Adopting editorial management tools to reflect changes to the business model
 - Modifying article templates with language for open licences and copyright
 - Submitting an application to DOAJ

- If the journal is published by an organization or by a unit within a university, you may have have access to legal and procurement advice to help you with:
 - Taking stock of contracts and agreements
 - Implementing the chosen business model, establishing contracts with new service providers
 - Modifying contracts

- If the journal is associated with any professional and paraprofessional publishing organizations, such as the Canadian Association of Learned Journals, there may be helpful resources/services available to you through these networks.

- Érudit's blog series "5 questions with..." interviews journals about their various experiences, some of which cover transitions to diamond OA. The posts in particular could offer helpful anecdotal information to inform your journal's transition:
 - [Industrial Relations](#)
 - [AEQUITAS](#)
 - [Atlantic Geoscience](#)